

HARMONY OF MOTHERLAND AND MOTHER IMAGES IN POETRY

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Abstract. *In poetry, the image of the mother is reflected in the artistic whole with the concept of homeland. The issue of poetic harmony of the concept of mother and homeland. This article is analyzed on the example of the poetry of Abdulla Oripov, Amon Matjon, Khurshid Davron.*

Keywords. *Artistic integrity and generalized image, image and imagery, poetic image, lyrical character, love.*

An artistic image, a universe that embodies objective and subjective beginnings, reflects the creator's personality along with real reality. Therefore, each poem is a world, a product of the creator's imaginative thinking. An image that is a product of artistic thinking is defined as istilah as follows. A reflection of existence seen by an artist's eye and creatively processed on an ideal basis, expressed in a form that can be emotionally perceived [2.19]. The image, as a reworked unit of poetry, combines intelligence and feeling. According to the esoteric foundations of knowledge of the world, the original artistry belongs to Allah, the absolute power that created the Pen in the Muslim East, who, as the only and absolute creator, created man on his basis. The word was originally in God as a great weapon that created the world from nothing. Boundless worlds were created by a single command of the Creator. This endless weapon made man the dearest of all creatures in existence as a symbol of his power to create and destroy, to cause happiness and unhappiness. When the power of words, the power of the pen and the artistic thinking of the creative soul unite, an artistic image is born [3.72]. There are perfect creators who have the skill of creating a philosophical lyrical image, who can connect with the divine spirit, there are writers who have broken through the layers of imagination

of the human mind. Abdulla Oripov is one of such wise poets in Uzbek literature who has a unique style of image creation [2.35]. In the article, we will consider Abdulla Oripov's unique image of the mother, the combination of magnificent poetic images, common images of motherland and motherland. Looking at Abdulla Oripov's work, we notice that he often refers to the image of his mother. His poems include "Mother", "Letter to my mother", "Uzbek mother", "Ayol madhi", "The name mother", "Remembering my mother", "Childhood years", "Mother's mother", "To my mother's death". rs can be a vivid example of this. In some of Abdulla Oripov's poems dedicated to the image of the mother, the comparison of the mother to the motherland evokes new poetic thoughts and certain aesthetic feelings. To create such cast lines, every word should feel poetic [6.95]. In the poetry of Abdulla Oripov and the skill of image creation, we can see the love of Navoiyvor's wisdom. During the million-year life of the son of man on earth, the experiences of the ancestors created the most diverse forms of life on the planet. Based on these life experiences, a person has improved. Scholars write interesting opinions about people.

According to Farobi, according to his nature, a person needs other people to organize, strengthen and improve his life. According to Ibn Sina, man differs from all other animals in his language, intelligence and thinking. Although man is an incredibly perfect being, he is usually weaker than other creatures in nature at the time of his first birth. In the Qur'an, the concept of weakness in relation to man is mentioned 52 times in 45 verses. He will need a mother who surrounds him with strength and talent. As stated by Ibn Sina, the language elevates a person to the quality of a living creature. The word, the great weapon that created the world from nothing, is imprinted on the mind, heart, and tongue by the mother for the first time. Therefore, the name of the language is the mother tongue. Motherland is the name of the soil on which man first stepped. Because of this, there is no artist who does not honor his motherland and mother. The feeling of homeland is a feeling encoded

in the human mind from the mother's womb. As long as a person lives, this feeling grows, grows, and develops like his age. In the poetry of the wise poet Abdulla Oripov, we observe a harmonious image of the images of Motherland and Motherland. The poem called "The Name of Mother" attracts our attention. Before analyzing the poem, it is important to pay attention to its title. In modern Uzbek literature, the practice of naming poems is quite common. The main reason for this is the need for an ideological and artistic understanding, which the title fulfills. The value of the name "Mother" is reflected in the entire idea of the poem.

The title emphasizes the image that is the basis of the topic. The main text focuses on other important aspects of the image (unity in the mother, non-repetition). The name "Mother" is connected to the name "Vatan" and "Vatan" in turn is connected to the name "Mother".

They say they are a fierce price,
Brave when he gives his life in battle,
Endure the pains and rest,
They whisper one word: Mother[1.88].

As if the poet were telling a story, as if he were telling a fairy tale, he paints a picture of the momentary moments in the mind of the reader, when the fierce Bahadurs gave their lives on the battlefields. In this moment, the reader can see the images of the hero that are not written in the poem. Of course, if the student is smart. He can bring to mind the pains, the last breaths, and the last expressions on the faces of those who are angry. This scene is characteristic of the three lines of the poem, and in the fourth line, an important emotional idea is expressed, that the word "mother" is an afterword, the hero's dream, longing, pain, and farewell words on the eve of the journey from this world to another. uses instead of . Perhaps, while saying these words, the entire life of the hero will be sealed in one moment. No matter how strong and fierce the hero is, he feels his weak and kind mother in front of him. The last breath and the last word, "Mother." So even those who are full of strength and

power worship the mother when they are weak. If a person's last word is mother, then his eternal destination will be mother earth. In fact, such great conclusions, which are beyond the text of the poem, are hidden in every word of the master and wise poet. The poet actually puts support, inexhaustible strength, love and trust under the name mother.

A great sage commented on the universe,
Finally, he recognized the country where he was born.
With respect when speaking,
Mother, he called his tongue for the first time [1.89]

In the article "The Power of the Living Word", Suvon Meli compares the importance of words in everyday life and in poetry, describing: "In poetry, the word works with all its power." The poet's skill is that he can turn simple words into great power and wise thought without excessive allusions. In the first quatrain, the sanctity of the glorified Mother, her important quality in human life is emphasized, while in the second quatrain, another lonely and unique motif is compared to language. This is the meaning that stands out in the poem. But the great sage, in the path of the past time and space in the way of interpreting the world, got to know himself and his identity, through this he got to know the country he was born in, and through mother (yes, that's how) his language, consciousness, and worldview were formed. , it is said that he called the language his mother for the first time.

Abdulla Oripov, whether he writes about nature or the image of his mother, does not avoid the topic of his motherland. It illuminates the hero's understanding of his identity in the sacred space and time. Self-awareness begins with the awareness of the mother who brought her offspring into this bright world, and through the mother with the awareness of national values: the nation, history, and the world of religion. After these realizations, he calls the language his mother, the means of communication of people - the door to the heart. He glorifies the holy land that grew up in his bosom as his motherland.

Poets of the world for the honor of the Motherland

Adjectives are lined up and lined up,

Finally, the words have one meaning

Those who end up calling the motherland [1.89]

In the third quartet, it is the poets' turn. While poets are looking for a series of adjectives for the honor of the Motherland, they come to a conclusion on a word consisting of only three letters. Mother. We have the opportunity to observe the meaning of the word in this paragraph in two different meanings. They come to one meaningful idea. The meaning is unique, unique and unrepeatable, and they represent to the mother that the Motherland is also unique and unique. They conclude, Motherland. The image of the author is a price, he appears as a sage, a poet. Through the language of these images, the poet expresses his respect for the woman - mother, who contributed to the development of the thinking space and the human society existing in this space.

If it's good, it's worthless.

A word is colorless when repeated,

Motherland is one in this bright world.

There is only one name in the world called mother [1.89].

In the above three quatrains, the author expresses his thoughts in the language of images, and in the last quatrain, the author shows himself as a wise poet and son of the country, Abdulla Oripov. Even when it is said that it is a poem by Abdulla Oripov, the author is hidden, it will be fully visible in the conclusion. The poet shows that most of the honey is worthless and the powerful words become discolored when repeated. In order to avoid repetition, it indicates that only one word is needed as a native word. The final conclusion is that the suffix is Mother, the language is Mother's language, Motherland is Motherland, All of them are united by the unity of one holy word mother. The poet's artistic thinking brings this real reality to the level of a poetic image.

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